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Transportation and Storage Companies in OECD Countries

The number of transportation and storage companies in OECD countries grew by 36.31% between 2005 and 2022. The OECD calculates the number of transportation and storage companies in its member countries. The data covers the period from 2005 to 2022, including micro, small, medium, and large enterprises.

Transportation and Storage Companies in OECD Countries in 2022. An analysis of the number of transportation and storage companies in OECD countries for the year 2022 provides an overview of the economic and logistical dynamics within the region. Turkey leads the ranking with 572,213 companies, representing a significant component of the national economy. This figure indicates a robust logistics and transportation infrastructure, crucial for a country positioned as a bridge between Europe and Asia, and which has developed one of the region's most dynamic logistics sectors. France and Spain follow with 225,394 and 212,306 companies, respectively. These numbers reflect their strategic positions in Europe and their central roles in European and international trade. France, with its advanced transportation system and well-developed infrastructure network, supports a wide range of logistical activities. Spain, with its numerous ports and growing integration into global supply chains, has seen significant growth in the sector. Poland, with 169,607 companies, demonstrates the growing importance of Central and Eastern Europe as a logistics hub. Its strategic geographical position, combined with significant investments in transportation infrastructure, has made Poland a crucial point for freight transport in Europe. Italy, with 113,838 companies, continues to be a key player thanks to its well-developed transportation network and its central position in the Mediterranean. Germany, with 101,107 companies, despite its robust economy and dominant role in European trade, has a relatively lower number of companies compared to some of its neighbors. This can be explained by the presence of large logistics companies that dominate the market and the potential higher efficiency and consolidation of the sector. Countries like Romania and the Netherlands, with 99,104 and 65,365 companies, respectively, show a significant presence in the sector, with the Netherlands standing out for the port of Rotterdam, one of the largest and busiest in the world, serving as a gateway to Europe. Greece, with 62,007 companies, highlights the importance of maritime transport and the islands in the national logistics context. Hungary, the Czech Republic, Israel, and Portugal, with numbers ranging from about 42,995 to 46,892 companies, represent medium-sized economies with well-developed logistics sectors. Lithuania and Sweden, with 32,743 and 30,116 companies, respectively, demonstrate how even countries with smaller populations can have robust and diversified logistics sectors. Slovakia and Ireland, with 25,324 and 24,533 companies, reflect the importance of transportation and storage in export-oriented economies with strong international trade links. Finland, with 23,678 companies, benefits from its geographical

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position to facilitate trade between Europe and Russia. Bulgaria, Costa Rica, Belgium, and Norway, with figures ranging between 21,646 and 22,599 companies, represent economies with adequate logistics infrastructures to support national and international trade and distribution. Austria, Serbia, Croatia, and Denmark, with lower numbers, reflect a well-developed but smaller logistics structure compared to major European hubs. Slovenia, Latvia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Estonia, North Macedonia, Switzerland, Cyprus, Malta, and Luxembourg, with numbers ranging from 1,032 to 9,400 companies, represent smaller economies with logistics sectors adapted to their specific needs. Switzerland, despite its low number of companies, is known for its logistical efficiency and the importance of its transportation infrastructures, particularly in the railway and air sectors. In conclusion, the data show a significant variation in the number of transportation and storage companies among OECD countries, reflecting different economic sizes, geographical positions, and industrial structures. Countries with large logistics sectors, such as Turkey, France, and Spain, play a crucial role in global supply chains, while smaller nations like Luxembourg and Malta have sectors adapted to their specific economic needs.

Transportation and Storage Companies in OECD Countries between 2005 and 2022. An analysis of data on transportation and storage companies in OECD countries between 2005 and 2022 reveals significant trends and notable variations in both absolute and percentage terms. Slovakia recorded the highest percentage increase, with a growth of 1646.48%, rising from 1,450 to 25,324 companies. This exponential growth can be attributed to a combination of foreign investments, government incentives, and a strategic geographical position favoring international transport. Lithuania saw an increase of 470.04%, growing from 5,744 to 32,743 companies. This result reflects the country's ability to leverage its position as a gateway to Eastern and Northern European markets, along with favorable policies that have stimulated sector development. Romania also showed significant growth, with an increase of 310.25%, rising from 24,157 to 99,104 companies. Romania has benefited from increasing investments in transportation infrastructure and greater integration into European supply chains, facilitating sector growth. Ireland saw an increase of 291.65%, with the number of companies rising from 6,264 to 24,533. This increase was likely influenced by strong government support for SMEs and the attraction of multinationals using Ireland as a logistics hub for Europe. The Netherlands recorded a growth of 177.23%, increasing from 23,578 to 65,365 companies. The Netherlands, with its port of Rotterdam, plays a crucial role as a global logistics node, facilitating international trade. Costa Rica saw a growth of 164.61%, rising from 8,488 to 22,460 companies. This growth indicates the country's growing role as a logistics hub for Central and South America, benefiting from increased regional trade. France recorded an increase of 149.75%, rising from 90,248 to 225,394 companies. France's robust transportation infrastructure, combined with policies favorable to logistics sector development, has supported this growth. Other countries like Latvia and Estonia saw significant increases of 142.16% and 138.17%, respectively. These results reflect the growing importance of the Baltic states in European trade and their ability to develop efficient logistics sectors. In Portugal, the number of companies increased by 64.83%, rising from 26,084 to 42,995. This increase is partly due to investments in port and road infrastructures that have improved the country's logistical efficiency. Belgium and Hungary recorded more modest increases of 43.97% and 37.47%, respectively, but still show sustained growth due to improved infrastructures and integration into European supply chains. Austria, the Czech Republic, and Luxembourg saw increases of 21.40%, 20.18%, and 19.72%, respectively. These countries, with well-developed economies, have benefited from stable policies and advanced infrastructures supporting the logistics sector. Poland and Germany recorded increases of 17.81% and 17.42%, reflecting the continued growth of their logistics sectors in response to both internal and external demand. These countries are fundamental to European transport, with Germany acting as a central hub for continental trade. In Slovenia and Bulgaria, the increases were 16.44% and

13.44%, demonstrating steady but less dynamic growth compared to the top-ranking countries. Cyprus and Finland saw increases of 8.81% and 7.50%, respectively, while Sweden recorded a more modest growth of 4.85%. Norway, with an increase of 3.94%, reflects stable growth but is limited by its geographic and demographic context. Conversely, some countries have seen decreases in the number of transportation and storage companies. Spain saw a reduction of 4.22%, from 221,659 to 212,306 companies, which could be attributed to internal economic changes and sector restructuring. Greece recorded a decrease of 5.01%, from 65,275 to 62,007 companies, likely due to the economic crisis and structural challenges the country has faced in recent years. Denmark saw a decline of 12.38%, from 14,011 to 12,276 companies. This decline could reflect greater market concentration and the exit of less competitive companies. Italy recorded the most significant decrease, with a reduction of 23.34%, from 148,497 to 113,838 companies. This worrying figure reflects structural economic challenges and international competition negatively affecting the Italian logistics sector.

Economic Policies to Promote Transportation and Storage Companies in OECD Countries. Economic policies to promote transportation and storage companies in OECD countries are strategically oriented to improve the sector's efficiency, innovation, sustainability, and competitiveness. These policies include significant investments in infrastructure, such as the construction and improvement of ports, railways, roads, and airports, which are crucial to facilitating the efficient flow of goods. Countries like the Netherlands demonstrate how advanced infrastructure can support a globally relevant logistics sector. At the same time, technological innovation is promoted through tax incentives and funding for the adoption of advanced technologies, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), and blockchain, which enhance supply chain management, optimize logistics processes, and ensure greater transparency and traceability of goods. These technologies not only increase operational efficiency but also reduce costs and improve responsiveness to market demands. Training and skill development of the workforce are priorities, with professional training programs, apprenticeships, and refresher courses preparing workers to use new technologies and tackle the challenges of an evolving environment. In countries like Germany and France, collaborations between industries, universities, and training institutes create a highly skilled workforce ready to meet the needs of the modern logistics sector. Moreover, financial support in the form of grants, subsidized loans, and tax incentives is crucial to stimulate investments in the sector. Ireland, for example, attracts multinationals through a favorable tax regime, promoting the development of advanced logistics hubs and reducing the financial risk for companies, fostering innovation and the expansion of logistics operations. International cooperation and participation in regional and global trade agreements, such as the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) and the Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP), are fundamental to facilitating cross-border trade and improving the efficiency of global supply chains. These agreements reduce trade barriers and facilitate the flow of goods between member countries, stimulating the growth of the logistics sector. Collaboration with international organizations like the World Trade Organization (WTO) helps establish global standards and promote efficient logistics practices, strengthening the position of transportation and storage industries in international markets. Sustainability policies are becoming increasingly important, with the adoption of sustainable practices that reduce the environmental impact of logistics operations and improve energy efficiency. Countries like Sweden invest in green technologies, such as electric vehicles and low-impact transportation systems, and promote the use of renewable energy in storage operations. Tax incentives for the purchase of low-emission vehicles and grants for energy efficiency projects support the transition to a more sustainable logistics sector. These measures not only help reduce carbon emissions but also improve corporate image and respond to the growing consumer demand for more environmentally responsible business practices. Regulations and standards are essential to ensure that transportation and storage operations are safe,

efficient, and environmentally friendly. These regulations can include safety standards for transporting hazardous goods, energy efficiency requirements for storage buildings, and regulations to reduce pollutant emissions. Policies must be designed to be flexible and adaptable to rapid technological and market changes. Effective regulations incentivize companies to continuously improve their operational practices, contributing to a more competitive and sustainable logistics sector. Digitalization is another key area for modernizing the transportation and storage sector. The adoption of digital solutions, such as warehouse management systems (WMS) and transportation management platforms (TMS), improves operational efficiency, reduces costs, and increases supply chain visibility. Digitalization also facilitates data integration and collaboration among various supply chain actors. Policies that promote digitalization, such as funding for the implementation of digital technologies and training programs for digital skills, are essential to maintain the sector's competitiveness. Economic policies must also include incentives for innovation, such as funding for innovative startups and SMEs, acceleration and incubation programs, and support for industry-university collaboration. This stimulates the development of new technologies and solutions that improve the efficiency and sustainability of the logistics sector. Government programs offering grants and technical support for innovative projects can help transform promising ideas into practical solutions that enhance logistics operations.

Conclusions. The number of transportation and storage companies in the considered OECD countries grew by 36.31% between 2005 and 2022. Some countries have seen the number of transportation and storage companies grow much more than the average, such as Slovakia with +1646.48%, Lithuania with +470.04%, and Romania with +310.25%. However, there are also countries that have seen a reduction in the number of transportation and storage companies, such as Spain with -4.22%, Greece with -5.01%, Denmark with -12.38%, and Italy with -23.34%. Italy experienced the most significant reduction in absolute terms, with -34,659 companies between 2005 and 2022. In 2022, transportation and storage companies are distributed as follows: 26.80% are in Turkey, 10.56% in France, 9.94% in Spain, and 7.94% in Poland.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

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Appendix

Percentage Change in Number of Transport and Storage Enterprises (2005-2022) in OECD Countries

Number of Transport and Storage Enterprises in OECD Countries (2022)

